

From Peter to Mary: Rethinking the Theological Virtues of Faith, Hope and, Love

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Abstract: The theological virtues namely, faith, hope, and love (cf. 1 Cor. 13:13) are implicit in the affirmation of *Mysterium Fidei*. Christian understanding of faith is therefore the unity of knowing, hoping, and loving and are reciprocally related aspects of an existential genuine Christian way of Being. Christian faith not only includes the knowledge of certain content but also the response which justifies the decisions to believe. In the New Testament, the character of Mary is apt example of how the unity of faith, hope and love are manifested in their true meaning. However, comparing the character of Mary with the character of Peter in the Gospel of Mark, one can see the challenge of Christian discipleship poses for Christian way of living.

Keywords: Faith, Hope, Love, Mary, Peter, Ecclesiogenesis, *Mysterium Fidei*

Introduction

The New Testament accounts of Mary as a Biblical figure are very rare. However, these accounts powerfully present the true and

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enduring meaning of the Christian understanding of faith. So, it is no wonder then that, the New Testament accounts of Mary has produced four Marian dogmas, several doctrines, literature, and more devotional practices. So, this small study on Mary from the New Testament perspective is an attempt to illustrate that she is the embodiment of theological virtues, namely faith, hope, and love.

The heart of Christian Mystery is to confess that the incarnate and the crucified Son of God is risen from the dead to give us the Holy Spirit. Every faithful is regularly called to affirm this Mystery of faith, very particularly at the Eucharist, after the Institution Narrative, i.e., *Mysterium Fidei*: “Your death we proclaim, O Lord, and your resurrection we confess until you come” (cf. 1 Cor. 15:14ff).¹ The theological virtues namely, faith, hope, and love (cf. 1 Cor. 13:13) are implicit in this affirmation of *Mysterium Fidei*. Our *faith* in Jesus is that he is the Lord (cf. Rom. 10:11; Phil. 2:10); however, his lordship is proclaimed on the Cross (cf. 1 Cor. 1:23) which is the true and ultimate act of God’s *Love* (cf. Jn. 15:3). While crucifixion is an act of humans to thwart God’s plan of salvation,² God, in raising Jesus from death - we have been given hope a trustworthy hope (cf. Rom. 8:24, Heb. 10:22; Benedict XVI, *Spe salvi* 1), that God will not fail who puts trust in him.

¹ And this is the heart of the Gospel according to St. Paul. “...that Christ died for our sins, in accordance with the scriptures, and that he was buried; and that on the third day, he was raised to life, in accordance with the scriptures (1 Cor. 15: 1-4).

² Pope Francis has aptly articulated; “Jesus suffered betrayal by the disciple who sold him and by the disciple who denied him. He was betrayed by the people who sang hosanna to him and then shouted: ‘Crucify him!’ (Mt 27:22). He was betrayed by the religious institution that unjustly condemned him and by the political institution that washed its hands of him” (Pope Francis, “Homily. Palm Sunday 5 April 2020”)

Presupposition

T. Aquinas's famous definition of faith states that "believing is an act of the intellect assenting to the divine truth by command of the will moved by God through grace" (STh II-II, 2, 9). A holistic approach to faith includes an *assent* (to the content of Christian revelation), that is formed by the decision to *hope* (the eschatological dimension of faith) and completed by the practice of *love*. Faith, hope, and love are reciprocally related aspects of an existential genuine Christian attitude. A genuine principle of love includes faith because faith and love condition and demand each other reciprocally. Similarly, in the principle of love there is also present the principle of hope, which looks beyond the present that seeks the whole.³ Therefore, Christian understanding of faith is the unity of *knowing, hoping, and loving*, (Alfaro, 1982: 341) and cannot be separated. What we are trying to achieve here is to demonstrate that these three virtues can be found in Mary as portrayed by the Evangelist Luke in his gospel. And Mary as a model of faith become clear, when we compare her with the character of Peter in the Gospel of Mark.⁴

³ "Of course, the principle of love, if it is to be genuine, includes faith. Only thus does it remain what it is. For without Faith, which we have come to understand as a term expressing man's ultimate need to receive and the inadequacy of all personal achievement, Love becomes an arbitrary deed. It cancels itself out and becomes self-righteousness: Faith and Love condition and demand each other reciprocally. Similarly, in the principle of Love there is also present the principle of hope, which looks beyond the moment and its isolation and seeks the whole. Thus, our reflections finally lead of their own accord to the words in which Paul named the main supporting pillars of Christianity: 'So Faith, Hope, Love abide, these three; but the greatest of these is Love' (1 Cor 13:13)" (Ratzinger, 2004: 270).

⁴ Peter is presented as a spokesperson for Jesus's disciples. Therefore, Peter's reaction simply reflects the thought of the Twelve and is, therefore, not considered a character or individual distinct from the Twelve. As a

We need to keep in mind that Biblical Narrative Criticism, which also studies the way figures and persons are presented in the Gospel, lets us know that the figures reveal the Evangelist's theological outlook and the purpose of writing the gospel. Gospels do not give us descriptive accounts of the "what really happened"; characters act and speak and it is through their acting and speaking that they are revealed. So, Mary and Peter are not only, in the first place, historical persons but rather characters in the gospel *narratives* with a particular purpose (Lonsdale, 1984: 133-145; Vorster, 1987: 58). They are constructs that reflect an author's attempt to relate the *story of Jesus* for a specific theological purpose and persuade his reader, particularly those who most probably heard the narrative but did not see it individually. However, there can be difference of opinions (Vorster, 59, 73). Their ultimate aim is to tell the truth about Jesus Christ as the revelation of God and how this revelation affected the saints of early Christianity and, thereby, invites a faith response from present readers.⁵

So, 1) we are going to evaluate the character of Peter in the Gospel of Mark and how the characterization of Mary in the Gospel of Luke stands out better and complements it;

2) what the faithful can derive from these characters in understanding the theological virtues of faith, hope, and love. And, finally, what prompts such theological reflection is the understanding that the whole Bible needs to be taken as one book. Vatican II teaches that:

spokesperson Peter is viewed as a "type" rather than an individual. He represents the disciples and their failure (Whitaker, 2013: 667ff.).

⁵ R. Brown, for example, argues that Luke's main concern in the Infancy Narrative is not to get into the mind of the historical Mary at the scene of the Annunciation, but "to tell the reader how the child was conceived and hence to explain his identity" (Brown, 1993: 307).

Since Holy Scripture must be read and interpreted in the sacred spirit in which it was written, no less serious attention must be given to the content and unity of the whole of Scripture, if the meaning of the sacred texts is to be correctly worked out. The living tradition of the whole Church must be taken into account along with the harmony which exists between elements of the faith (*Dei Verbum* 12).

And Ratzinger also notes that:

The basic and primary presupposition of theological exegesis is, therefore, the conviction that Scripture – the multiplicity of its authors and its long historical genesis notwithstanding- is *one* book having a real intrinsic unity in the midst of its various tensions. This presupposition rests in turn upon the firm belief that Scripture is ultimately the work of a single author, who has both a human and a divine aspect (Ratzinger, 2005: 39)

Faith: Mary Is Blessed Because She Has believed

Fundamental to Christian faith proclaiming Jesus is the Lord-*Kyrios*, that is, the New Testament Faith, which Paul formulated in his confession of faith. “I live in faith in Jesus Christ “Son of God, who Loved me and gave himself for me” (Gal. 2:20). (Fries, 1996: 77). Paul’s confession affirms that the Christian faith is a personal ‘faith in Jesus Christ’ as well as an affirmational/propositional faith, i.e., faith in the Son of God “who loves me and gives himself for me”. Theologically speaking, an experience of the person of Jesus gradually evolves into a confession or a declaration that Jesus is the Christ, the *Messiah*. The confession of Paul brings to light the importance and the difficulty of Christian faith, namely, that Christian confession in Jesus Christ is not only to inform but also to move, to effect, to make an impact. (Fries, 1996: 77) This is the difficulty that we can encounter in Peter’s confession (cf. Mk. 8:27-30).

a. Impulsive Peter

Jesus' messianic claims at the scene at Caesarea Philippi is an important gospel passage about the discussion on Jesus' identity (also Mk 9.27-33). Peter's confession about Jesus, "you are the Christ" (Mk. 8:29) is a summarized declaration of Jesus's identity. However, Peter is portrayed here as an impulsive who reacted to Jesus' query on the spur of the moment (Mk 8:32, also 14:28)⁶ At first glance Peter's confession that Jesus is the Messiah is a very "positive" declaration. But the impression is very strongly corrected, as Peter's immediate reaction to the passion prediction is a refusal to accept the suffering of the Son of man. Peter misconceives Jesus' mission and his identity. Therefore, he opposes Jesus instead of helping him (Vorster, 1987: 71-73; Whitaker, 2013: 667). Peter's misconception arises from the fact that the identity of Jesus as revealed does not fit Peter's expectation. The revelation of Jesus as suffering Messiah does not move Peter because of his hardness of heart;⁷ rather he wishes to move his master according to his desire. Peter is rebuked promptly because he hesitatingly wished to fulfill the task of a follower in terms of 8:34-9:1; and we see in the latter part of the Gospel that Peter, as an unobtrusive follower, becomes aware of his lack of insight.

b. Pondering Mary

Luke's Gospel introduces Mary in 1:26-27, in a few brief points. She lived in a very insignificant place, in the town of Galilea named Nazareth (1:26). Well known are the sarcastic comments of

⁶ Peter is a person who at first sight is willing to obey. He promises to follow Jesus even if everybody else falls away and insists that he will not deny Jesus (Mk. 14:28ff) but in the end he fails ... when he realizes it, he bursts into tears (cf. Mk. 14:72) (cf. Vorster, 1987: 65).

⁷ Nevertheless, it is argued that Peter's and the disciples' incomprehension is due to their hardness of heart, and it serves the Christological function of heightening the Mystery of Jesus' identity. Because Jesus' identity is a Mystery, the disciples cannot grasp it without the help of divine assistance (Matera, 1989: 153-172).

Nathaniel, “can anything good come out of Nazareth” (Jn. 1:46). God chose a young girl from this lowly place to become the mother of the Messiah (Sri, 2012: 2). Mary is a *virgin* who is *betrothed*. In first century, Judaism, betrothal represented the first stage of a two-step marriage process different from engagement” in modern society. At a betrothal in Mary’s day, the bride and groom formally exchanged consent in the presence of witnesses (cf. Mal 2:14). This forged a legal bond between the two who would then be considered married. The woman would be called the groom’s “wife” (see Matt. 1:20, 24) and this union could only be broken by divorce. Any violation of the man’s marital rights would be considered adultery. After the betrothal, the wife usually remained living at her family home for up to a year. Then occurred the second step of the marriage process, ‘taking’ the wife to the man’s home. It was then that the man’s support for his wife and marital sexual relations formally began. So, Mary is legally married to Joseph, but she is not yet to the second stage of the marriage (Sri, 2012: 3-5). Mary is “troubled” by the greetings of the angel Gabriel (Lk. 1:26-29), and she is said to be afraid, which is why the angel Gabriel told her “do not be afraid...” (Lk. 1:30) and she *asks a question* because: 1) of the human impossibility involved in conceiving a child; 2) cultural shock because she is not yet living with her husband. The announcement to Mary is completely unheard of and has no biblical prototype for her to consider.⁸ Thus Mary’s query is about the process, not proof for this birth. (Sri, 2012, 12). However against the human impossibility, she is told that “with God, nothing will be impossible”, and she is given a similar sign - her elderly kinswoman Elizabeth is pregnant (Lk. 1:36-37). Mary becomes obedient to this

⁸ For instance, the ancient roots of God’s covenant people first sprouted with God’s gift of a son (Isaac) to a nonagenarian barren woman (Sarah) and her century-old husband (Abraham) (Gen. 17:15-22; 21:1-7) and that, at another critical junction in Israel’s history, God listened to the prayers of a desperate childless woman (Hannah) in the sanctuary and granted her a son as well (Samuel) (1 Sam. 1:1-20; cf. Jdgs. 13:2-25) (Sri, 2012: 12).

revelation and even enthusiastic in her response that she is the handmaid of the Lord, “let it be to me according to your *Word*”. By showing Mary’s readiness to obey the word of God (*rema*), Luke is here already presenting Mary as one of “those who hear the word of God (*logos*) and do it or keep it” (Lk. 8:21; 11:28).⁹ Thus, along with her unique mission of being Jesus’ physical mother, she is identified with archetypal faith for “everyone who like her is a handmaiden or servant of God can be a mother of Jesus who lets the divine word become flesh in his or her own body” (Balthasar, 2005: 139). Against this background we can recognize in Mary as a model of faith; namely, 1) in her obedience to the word of God, 2) in her capacity to dialogue with God, 3) and in her discernment of the process of participation in God’s salvific plan.¹⁰

The depth of her faith is well illustrated in her *Magnificat*. It embodies the joy of Mary who knows that Yahweh is faithful in his promises to her forefathers. She becomes the spokesperson of those Poor Ones whom God had helped by his might, whether they were women yearning for children or Israel reduced by oppression to the status of a “handmaid” (1 Mac. 2:11) of “low estate” (1 Sam. 9: 16). She is confident that Yahweh is going to bring blessings to those who fear him, and she could attest to it in a personal way because she had been assured by the angel, “for God nothing will be impossible” (Lk.1:37) (Brown, 2005: 361-362). She is hopeful that Yahweh will not fail her in her mission of being Jesus’ physical mother.

⁹ Luke is here already presenting Mary as one of “those who hear the word [*logos*] of God and do it” by placing on Mary’s lips at the end of the Annunciation scene: “Behold the handmaid of the Lord. Let it happen to me according to your word [*rema*]” (l: 38) (Brown, 1993: 318).

¹⁰ God who appreciates human freedom, “himself wanted in sovereign freedom to become man in her, the lowly handmaiden” (Balthasar, 2005: 139).

Love as Kenosis

Mary remains with her Son at the Cross when the other disciples run away (Jn 19: 25). Nothing could separate her from the love of God [revealed] in Christ Jesus (cf. 8: 31-9) (O'Collins, 2011: 143).

a. The Reluctant Peter

Peter's confession of Jesus as the Messiah is not without a foundation. It is argued that even during the lifetime of Jesus, i.e., before Easter, there existed among the disciples the understanding that Jesus is the Christ, that is the Messiah. Some of the disciples who were close to the movements of Zealots thought of political messiahship.¹¹ But Jesus had already rejected such an interpretation of his activity. However, Peter's confession is related to the prophetic tradition of the anointed, i.e., Jesus as the messenger and embodiment of God's final word who demands absolute obedience. According to this tradition, the Messiah is the prophet of the last times anointed with the Holy Spirit (Kasper, 2011: 94). However, Jesus rebukes Peter, because Jesus transcends this idea¹² or develops it "in his saying about the divinely ordained necessity for suffering" (Kasper, 2011: 94).¹³ According to G. O. Collins, the key to understand Jesus as suffering Messiah is in his preaching of the

¹¹ This means there existed a conflicting understanding about the concept of Messiahship (Whitaker, 2013: 670).

¹² G. O'Collins argues that "It would seem almost unaccountably odd if Jesus had never reflected on and applied to himself the Jewish conviction that the righteous suffer but God will vindicate them (Pss. 27, 37,38, 41, 55,69, 109) In Psalm 22 (and the other psalms) the righteous person does not die, but after severe sufferings is delivered and vindicated by God in the course of this life" (Id., 1995: 70-71).

¹³ While there may be traces of such ideas in the Jewish tradition, they are foreign to Peter not only here in Caesarea Philippi but also on Good Friday... because such ... messianic expectations could give rise to political misinterpretations of the messianic movement this might set off among the people could lead to accusation and condemnation] (Kasper, 2011: 94). This is one of the reasons the crowd, who sang Hosanna on his Triumphant entry into Jerusalem, rejected him before Pilate.

Kingdom of God. “Jesus saw suffering and persecution as characterizing the coming of that kingdom which he insistently preached. The message of the Kingdom led more or less directly to the Mystery of the passion” (O’Collins, 2011: 72). During his trial, Jesus never denies that he is the Messiah, otherwise he would call into question his mission and preaching of the Kingdom of God; because in his life Jesus had claimed that the Kingdom of God has *already* come (cf. Matt. 11:4; Lk. 7:22).

[Therefore Jesus’...] mission culminated in the suffering ordeal to come: a time of crisis and distress which was to move towards the day of the Son of Man (Mk. 13 parr.), the restoration of Israel (Matt. 19:28 par.), the banquet of the saved, and the salvation of the nations (Matt. 8: 11 par.). Thus, his arrest, trial, and crucifixion dramatized the very thing which totally engaged Jesus, that rule of God which was to come through a time of ordeal (O’Collins, 2011: 72).

Therefore, Jesus accepts that he is the Suffering Messiah, the Messiah of the Cross, and invites and prepares disciples to accept this truth (cf. Mk. 14:25). “[The] essential connection between the message of Jesus and his person meant that the vindication of his person in and through death entailed the vindication of God’s kingdom, and vice versa” (O’Collins, 2011: 73), which Jesus envisages is a cosmic and eschatological triumph (Mk. 8:38) whereas Peter hoped for triumph at an historical level (Mk. 8:33) and, therefore, he rebuked Jesus words about his suffering (Whitaker, 2013 : 670).¹⁴

¹⁴ “If dominion is a mark of the Messiah, Jesus’ dominion takes the form of service. If the Messiah’s path to dominion leads through struggle and victory, Jesus’ path points towards suffering and defeat. . . In the dominion of service which includes suffering which comes from thinking God’s thoughts, . . . we begin to see the new understanding of Messiahship which prevented Jesus from letting himself be called

Peter's failure is in the rebuke; for the word often used in the Gospel of Mark to admonish and to rebuke one's Master is not expected from a disciple.¹⁵ Jesus' "rebuke" response also befits the manner of one who wants to correct the disciple's idea of his status. Thus Jesus' "get behind me" and "If any man would come after me, let him deny himself and take up his Cross and follow me" (Mk 34).

What Peter is currently doing standing in front of Jesus is rebuking him as if he, Peter, is the teacher. Consequently, Jesus' words are simultaneously a rebuke and a recall to adopt the correct posture of a true disciple - one who follows and who thinks according to the divine way and not the human way (8:33) (Whitaker, 2013: 673).

Jesus certainly saw that his proclamation of the Kingdom of God and his impending suffering could not be separated because his redemptive service, his option for the poor and the marginalized, won him, from the very beginning, the hostility of his opponents (cf. Mk. 2:1-12). Following Jesus means following him in this service of Love: 'If anyone would be first, he must be last of all and servant of all' (Mk. 9:35). A life like this involves being prepared for anything, leaving everything (cf. Mk. 10:28), even risking your life (cf. Mk. 8.34-35). Jesus saw his own fate prefigured in that of the prophets who were persecuted and rejected in Jerusalem (cf. Mk. 12:1-12). Jesus wanted to alert his disciples that opting for him does not mean peace, but a break with the *status quo* and they will meet the same fate as he will (cf. Mk. 8.34) (Kasper, 2011: 104-108). "His

Messiah, since that title would only have encouraged misunderstanding of his mission" (Kasper, 2011: 94-95).

¹⁵ On the lips of Jesus, rebuke is a powerful action word. It is used against chaotic nature and to demons who knew Jesus' true identity (Mk. 1:25; 3:12; 4:39; 8:30,33; 9:25); as a command to be silent or to keep his identity hidden (Mk. 1:25; 3:12; 4:39; 8:30); in the stilling of the stormy wind (Mk. 4:39); and in Jesus's command to unclean spirit to exit a person (Mk. 1:25; 9:25) (Whitaker, 2013: 671).

death on the Cross is the culmination of that turning of God against himself in which he gives himself in order to raise man up and save him. This is Love in its most radical form” (Benedict XVI, *Deus Caritas est*, 12). In the aftermath of Easter, Peter will be reinstated and can become pastor to Christ’s flock only after he has three times testified to his love (Jn. 21: 15–19) (O’Collins, 2011: 143).

b. The Cruciformity of Mary’s Faith

Faith responses and commitments need to be actualized by the decision the faithful make. The Cruciformity of faith means that one demonstrates faith conviction by one’s obedient, self-emptying act which Christ exhibited on the Cross. In other words, the self-emptying act of Christ shapes Christian commitments and attitudes in all circumstances.

Luke presents Mary as the faithful remnant in whom all the important aspects of the promises of the Old Testament to the daughter of Zion are fulfilled.¹⁶ The Cruciformity of faith is evident in Mary’s pilgrimage of faith (Ratzinger, 2005: 50). First, Mary’s faith was tested when “the bombshell virgin birth” announcement was dropped by Gabriel. In her socio-religious background, according to the law of Moses (cf. Dt. 22:22; Lev. 20:10), to be found with a child before coming to live with her betrothed was a

¹⁶ That is why the angel addressed her as “Hail Mary; E. Sri argues that “Hail” (Lk. 1:28) is reminiscent of the Daughter Zion oracles and this interpretation fits with the many royal messianic themes in the Annunciation scene. “Hail,” in Greek *Chaire*, is literally a command to “rejoice.” And this brings to mind the mysterious Daughter Zion figure of the Old Testament and signals that prophecy is coming to fulfillment and God is coming to Israel as King. In the Old Testament, particularly in the Prophets, “Daughter Zion” is a symbolic figure representing the Faithful remnant of God’s people, i.e., the Faithful people of Israel who were awaiting the messianic age (Zep. 3:14-15; Zec 9:9. “Sons of Zion” in Joel 2:23) is a similar image. The prophets foretold that they would rejoice because the Lord the King would liberate them from their enemies (cf. Sri, 2018: 14ff).

disgraceful situation. Thus, Luke highlights the realism of Mary's challenge while presenting her as the faithful remnant. Secondly, although what is being revealed to her remains a Mystery (cf. Lk. 2:48 and John Paul II, *Redemptoris Mater*, 17), her response to God, "let it be with me according to your word" (Lk. 1:38), is with strong conviction. Mary continues to repeat her faithful response at every new circumstance during her faith journey, namely, Mary's encounter with the aged Simeon and Hanna, and in her losing and finding Jesus in the Temple. Knowing that she is dealing with mystery, she prefers to keep it in her heart (Lk. 2:19; 2:51; cf. 1:29; 2:33). She does not become a hindrance to her son's mission; she rather affirms her faith in walking with her son towards Calvary. Against this background, John Paul II teaches that:

On that wood of the Cross her Son hangs in agony as one condemned. "He was despised and rejected by men; a man of sorrows...he was despised, and we esteemed him not": as one destroyed (cf. Is. 53:3- 5). How great, how heroic then is the obedience of faith shown by Mary in the face of God's "unsearchable judgments"! How completely she "abandons herself to God" without reserve... Through this faith, Mary is perfectly united with Christ in his self- emptying. This is perhaps the deepest "kenosis" of Faith in human history (*Redemptoris Mater* 18).

Through her pilgrimage of faith, she participates in and makes present the Mystery of Christ to the world. "The *Pietà* completes the picture of the Cross because Mary accepts the Cross, the Cross communicating itself in Love, the Cross that now allows us to experience in her compassion the compassion of God" (Ratzinger, 2005: 78-79). In her *Magnificat* she highlights the *depth* of her faith conviction that God will not abandon his faithful. The *Pietà*, i.e., at the Cross she achieves the *integrity* of her faith pilgrimage. Therefore, in her faithful response (Lk. 1:26-38), Luke portrays Mary as the epitome of the metaphor of the Daughter of Zion, in

other words, all that God wishes to realize for his people by his salvific action (Potterie, 1992: 3).¹⁷

Hope - God Will Not Fail Us

The resurrection of Jesus which makes the Gospel the good news because it contains fidelity of God, who is infinitely greater and more powerful than human persons and who can counsel and help when human beings find themselves at the end of their own wisdom and strength.

a. Peter and the Hopeless Situation

A person who yields to the temptation to evade the Cross is not a person of hope, because he cannot see beyond the Cross. Even in the passion prediction, Jesus says that after three days he will rise again (Mk. 8:31). The impulsive Peter immediately rebuked Jesus in the prediction of his Passion. However, Jesus rebukes Peter and addresses him as Satan, an unambiguously negative term. One possibility put forward is that, like the demonic forces, Peter perceives who Jesus really is and is thus described as behaving like the Satan: 1) Jesus was tempted by Satan in the wilderness to find

¹⁷ According to de la Potterie, God is a loving father. Although God showed how he felt toward the rebellious Israelites, he also had an eye for the future when the relationship would be restored and he could once again return to them and welcome them into his arms (cf. Zech. 2:10; 9:9). In the Old Testament, Zion is imaged as Spouse and Daughter. “Here the Old Testament texts of the ‘Daughter of Zion’ are applied to a definite woman. ... This is precisely the reason why, in the Fourth Gospel, both at Cana and at the Cross, Jesus addresses Mary calling her ‘Woman’”... The particular woman Mary, the Mother of Jesus, is in a certain way the historical realization of this symbolic figure who is called in by the prophets, depending on the context, the ‘Daughter of Zion, the Mother-Zion, or the Virgin Israel. All of Israel’s expectation of salvation was projected upon this symbolic figure of the ‘Messianic Daughter of Zion’; this symbolic figure, described by the prophets, is concretized at once in a daughter of Israel, Mary, who thus becomes the personification of the messianic people in eschatological times” (Potterie, 1992: 17-18).

shortcuts to still his hunger and to find glory. Peter's language is similar to the language of Satan, while Peter accepts that Jesus is Messiah, he never wanted the divinely willed plan of messiahship. 2) In other parts of the New Testament Satan is portrayed as a 'blinder' associated with darkness and incomprehension rather than light (cf. 2 Cor 4:4; Acts 18; Whitaker, 2013: 673) So, Peter as a spokesperson for the disciples, is behaving in a way that blinds others from seeing the path of true discipleship. Peter thought that if Jesus were to die at the hand of the Jews, then the Jesus' movement would be over.

b. Mary at Pentecost. Symbol of Hope – Matured in Faith

Mary's journey with her son does not end at Calvary, her faith looks beyond the Cross. She lives with the community of disciples in prayer in the days leading up to the descent of the Holy Spirit. Mary's presence at Pentecost is quite significant because Pentecost echoes the event of the Annunciation at Nazareth. Jesus Christ had at that time been conceived of the Holy Spirit and now, at Pentecost, the Holy Spirit brings forth a new community, the Church. and Mary unite these two great moments in the history of salvation (John Paul II, *Redemptoris Mater*, 24; Ratzinger, 2005: 57).

The angel Gabriel, as the messenger of God, strengthens Mary at the Annunciation by the promise that by the power of the Most High the Holy Spirit will overshadow her. At Pentecost the disciples are strengthened by the post Resurrection appearance of Jesus Christ. By his command they were not to depart from Jerusalem until clothed with the power from on high (cf. Lk. 24. 49; Acts. 1: 3-5). The disciples gather with Mary at the Upper Room (cf. Acts. 1:14) and received the Baptism of the Holy Spirit (cf. Acts 2:1-4) to become a new self-generating community. The faith of Mary as the prototypical hearer of the Word makes possible the bodily conception of Jesus. She bears the Word and keeps it. Mary's faith reaches its maturity at Pentecost, by accompanying the disciples in that event. The Church participates in the archetypal faith of Mary

when the Church spiritually brings forth individuals through the sacrament of Baptism; a new generation of People believing, hoping, and loving again.

Concluding Reflections

Biblical faith expresses the conviction that God's plan of salvation reveals itself in human history for humanity's sake (cf. Dt. 26:5-11). Biblical figures tell us not only how God acted in their history but also that it has a message for us today. Our discussion on the theological virtues of faith, hope, and love is an attempt to understand *how* these virtues play out in the New Testament figures of Mary and Peter within the Mystery of Christ. Based on our studies we can conclude our findings under three headings, namely, Christological (*Faith*), Eschatological (*Hope*), and Ecclesial (*Love*).

Christological (Faith)

Because within the Mystery of Christ the role of Mary and Peter in the New Testament evolves and develops, we can say that our study on the theological virtues is also Christological. We began this study with the question Jesus himself put to his disciples, "Who do you say that I am?" (Mk. 8:29) - a Christological question around which fundamental Christian faith stands.

Both Mary and Peter have their faith tested concerning the question of the Messiah. Mary was asked if she could be the mother of the Messiah-King, i.e., the Incarnation, Peter was asked if he could follow the suffering Messiah, i.e., the King of the Cross. However, the difference is found in their response, but a similarity can be discerned in the God providence. In the last analysis what we see is that the will of God will succeed. God saves both the good and the bad.

a. Mary as the Handmaid in the Mystery of Christ

From the Annunciation to Pentecost Mary stands in the New Testament as a model for all Christians in her faith and discipleship. Mary's life is uniquely related to the decisive moment (*Kairos*= Gal. 4:4-7) in the history of salvation, because she opened the door of the world for the definitive coming of the redeeming God into the flesh of our humanity (Rahner, TI- I 1961: 201-14; 202-3). Her singular position in God's saving plan very much dependent on the Mystery of Christ which lies at the very heart of the dogma of the Immaculate Conception. "...that the Blessed Virgin Mary, at the first instant of her conception, by a singular privilege and grace of the Omnipotent God, in virtue of the merits of Jesus Christ, the Savior of mankind, was preserved immaculate from all stain of original sin..." (Pius IX, *Ineffabilis Deus*). The dogma links "Mary to the merits of Christ that would have been applied to her by anticipation or retroactively. The Son's merits flowed back upon the mother, not in the irreversible temporality of history but in the sovereign mind of God the Creator who makes all creatures what they are" (Tavard, 1996: 195). It is the God and not the sinful conduct of the ancestors, that gives being to the creature.

Along with her unique role, the dogma teaches she was chosen by the Triune God to be the *Theotokos*, to be a "worthy" God-bearer (Jelly, 1992: 276). Dogma demonstrates the abiding being of God who desires to be with humankind in this world. Therefore, the Church teaches that "only in the Mystery of Christ is her Mystery made clear" (John Paul II. *Redemptoris missio* 4; cf. 19).¹⁸ If Scripture is the account of God's action in human history, the Church dogmas teach the eternal truth that is hidden in God's

¹⁸According to Vatican II: 'Devoutly meditating on her and contemplating her in the light of the Word made man, the Church reverently penetrates more deeply into the great Mystery of the Incarnation and becomes more and more like her spouse,' *Lumen Gentium*, no. 65.

revelation. The Marian Dogmas teach about the Mystery of Christ and this has been well elucidated in the words of Balthasar:

The statement that Mary is *theotokos*, the one who gives birth to God, is in the first place a statement which has its rightful setting in Christology. The statement that her conception was immaculate is in the first place a statement whose setting is the doctrine of grace and redemption. The statement that she is a virgin, in order that she may become the Mother of Christ – In itself a simple repetition of the witness of Scripture – is in the reflection of the Church a statement taken from the theology of the Covenant and consequently from the doctrine of the people of the Church. And the dogma of the Assumption of her body into heaven is, properly understood, a part of the universal Christian doctrine of the Last Things (Balthasar, 1975: 65).

In the conclusion to his brief survey of post-conciliar Mariology, A. Dulles concisely states:

There can be no cleavage between the Mary of history and the Mary of dogma. By a neglect of history, one can open the path to a divinized Mary in whom mythical projection overcomes theology. By a neglect of dogma one can deprive Mary of her distinctive role in salvation history and reduce her to the common level of humanity (Dulles, 2002: 219).

Within the “hierarchy of truths,”¹⁹ as taught by Vatican II, the primary or central truths are the Trinity, Incarnation, and Redemption. The function of Marian dogmas or revealed truths is to shed light upon the central mysteries of our Christian faith and

¹⁹ “When comparing doctrines with one another, they should remember that in Catholic doctrine there exists a “hierarchy” of truths, since they vary in their relation to the fundamental Christian faith (*Unitatis redintegratio*, 11).

also to inspire us to live more fully in fidelity to them. They have as well soteriological and ecclesiological aspects which help enlighten us about the central Mystery of our redemption by Christ alone and inspire us to more devoted discipleship (Jelly, 1992: 276). Mary's uniqueness is to be found in her distinctive role which she faithfully accomplished. We can situate Mary's distinctive role within God's plan of salvation who desires that all to be saved (1 Tim. 2:4) and everyone who is called by God according to his purpose has a unique role to fulfill in his/her life (cf. Eph. 1:3; 2:10). For which, as Vatican II taught that she is the "type and excellent exemplar in faith and charity."

While type and exemplar, Mary is also member of the Church. This limits her exemplarity in a sense; she should not, for example, be made out to possess all the different graces and charisms given to the members of the Church, as certain authors did in the past in an effort to explain how she is "full of grace." Rather, the Council considers her in the history of salvation and concludes that in her personal role and virtues she is type of the Church and exemplar for everyone in the Church. In yet a more positive direction, because she is member, Mary as type enters into the reality of the Church. She is type and exemplar from within the Church, sharing the Church's life (Neumann, 1986: 122).

The Catechism of the Catholic Church's teaching on "Mary - Mother of Christ, Mother of the Church", states that "Mary's function as mother of men in no way obscures or diminishes this unique mediation of Christ, but rather shows its power" (CCC 916, cf. LG 60). In Christ everyone is called and is destined in love to be God's sons and daughters (cf. Eph. 1:3; Rom. 8:28). The Holy Spirit who overshadows Mary at the Incarnation of Jesus is the same Spirit who makes us a new creation by forgiving our sin and giving us

faith, hope, and love.²⁰ Considering the nature of Mary's Faith as it is manifested from the Annunciation onwards, namely, her self-entrustment to God's faithful Love and her promise to be the Mother of the Savior, will help the faithful to understand that *believing* in God involves offering oneself unconditionally (*loving*) to God's plan.

Peter and the Cost of Discipleship

Peter as a biblical figure demonstrates the difficulty in following Christ where one encounters the cost of discipleship. Although Jesus rebukes Peter, he is allowed to accompany Jesus on special occasions (cf. Mk. 5:37f.; 8:27ff.; 13:3ff.), particularly at the Transfiguration (Mk. 9:2ff) (Vorster, 1987: 73). And Peter goes along with Jesus to Jerusalem. Peter, who so emphatically claimed to die with Jesus, makes as far as the courtyard (14:66), and was, literally, the last man standing. All the other male disciples had fled (14:50-51). He is not a non-follower of Jesus in Mark's Gospel. He is present during Jesus' trial although at a distance which is the mark of fallibility (Vorster, 1987: 70). And his fallibility of faith in Jesus reaches its zenith at a most critical situation: Peter denies his discipleship of Jesus three times and the scene ends poignantly. Peter, hearing the cock crow and *recalling what Jesus said* (14:30), *weeps* (14:72). *He disowned his master because he lost his hope in a powerless messiah thereby, he failed in loving Jesus, his master*

²⁰ St. Augustine, on the *Predestination of the Saints*, argues that all is God's gift, including the act of faith. Since God's grace and power to save are at the very heart of the gospel, it would be quite difficult to refute the biblical arguments that Augustine presents. We receive a share in "every spiritual blessing in the heavenly places" (Eph. 1:3) because God, from eternity and solely because of his own goodness and Love, willed that it be so. The Holy Spirit who overshadows Mary at the Incarnation of Jesus is the same Spirit who makes us a new creation by forgiving our sins and giving us faith, hope, and love. From eternity, God has predestined the Head and the members in the Head (cf. Eph. 1:3-6) (cf. Levering, 2013:122).

in his way to messiahship. When one's Faith in a person is no more a force to look forward, then the Love for that person gradually fades away. However, by presenting the poignant Peter who remembers what Jesus said and consequently weeping for his failure, Mark is communicating to the reader that Peter is preparing for his recall as Jesus' true disciple (Whitaker, 2013: 677). Here we see the transformation an impulsive to a pondering Peter.

Thus, at the end of the Gospel we see that the relationship of Peter (Mk. 16:7) with Jesus' followers is re-established (Vorster, 1987: 70). Peter is the only disciple mentioned by name at this point in the Gospel. While the character of Peter offers the meaning of cost of discipleship in following the suffering messiah, more confidently, Peter's character offers an example of one who failed Jesus twice but was forgiven and called to follow him again after failure (Whitaker, 2013: 681-682). He goes on to become an important figure in the Jerusalem community and to embrace martyrdom and to confess his ultimate love for his Master. (Whitaker, 2013: 678-679). Thus, he demonstrates the very meaning of the Mystery of Christ, namely, that God's Love wins over both the good and the bad.

b. Eschatological Dimension

“Who do you say that I am?” is an existential question to which in every generation the faithful must respond in their particular time and place. Therefore, reflection on Faith as a theological virtue does not become abstract but is rather an analysis of the act of Faith from the personal context in which it takes place.

In our exploration of the figure of Mary we have found that she is a person imbued with the virtue of hope. In the depth of her faith, she could praise God. She remembered the promise made to Abraham and his descendants (cf. Lk 1:55). She remained hopeful that the same God would guide her. Therefore, she could move on with her Son to the moment of Calvary (cf. Benedict XVI, *Spe Salvi*, 50). At

the Annunciation she was told that her Son would be called great and that he would sit on the throne of David his Father. Now he was dying in disgrace and her *Pietà* is nothing but a quiet still meditation on the Mystery of the Cross where she saw beyond “the power of God, and the wisdom of God” (1 Cor. 1:24). At the foot of the Cross thus we see the maturity of her Faith.

We have also seen that, although, Jesus had rebuked Peter for his reluctance to accept the suffering Messiah, Peter was not a non-follower. The joy of the resurrection touched him as well. Peter became a martyr for Christ because he understood that faith in Jesus needs to be demonstrated by following him in its existential context. A theology of hope is nothing but faith’s capacity to see beyond the present crisis and to live out to the belief that the providence of God will not abandon us (cf. Heb.11: 1)

c. Ecclesial Dimension

Two unique moments in the redemptive economy of grace are the incarnation of the Word and the birth of the Church. These two historic events are brought about through the action of the Holy Spirit. Mary links these two events through her pilgrimage she makes from Nazareth to the Upper Room in Jerusalem; a journey that expresses her fiat which is preserved in hope and anchored in her love of God.

We have stated that the Church participates in the archetypal faith of Mary when the Church lives out the theological virtues, namely, faith, hope, and love. This calls to mind the famous concept in the theology of the Church: *Ecclesiogenesis*, i.e., a dynamic vision of the Church’s self-realizing herself in the history. Against this background a much-quoted metaphorical saying of Venerable Bede is *Nam et Ecclesia quotidie gignit Ecclesiam*, – “Every day the Church gives birth to the Church” (Bede, II: XII) gains its significance. J. Komonchak, who has often quoted this statement interpreted it as follows. There are two inseparable moments in this

daily genesis of the Church, an objective moment, and a subjective reception. The objective moment refers to the constitutive meaning that centers around the life, teachings, death, and resurrection of Jesus Christ, which are represented in the Scriptures, in the tradition, in dogmas, in the liturgy etc. They are the objective principle of the unity of the Church across generations. When these objective principles are received and appropriated by each successive generation of Christians it becomes a subjective moment. But the objective meanings that make the Church a distinctive community do not affect the Church except in so far as they are received and appropriated by each successive generation of Christians in the Church's daily genesis (Komonchak, 1995: 89). Faith comes from hearing, St. Paul said, but he also said that no one can say Jesus is Lord except in the Holy Spirit. And it is the act of personal and communal appropriation of the Gospel that is the second, subjective moment in the Church's daily genesis.

Mary's Faith is archetypal because she shows us that God wants humankind to be fruitful. Mary actively demonstrates how to hear the message of salvation, and thus move from hearing to faith, from faith to hope and from hope to love. Thus, the journey she makes from the Annunciation to the Pentecost reveal her personal moments wherein she endured the faith trails, while anchoring securely in God's promises, and her love for her Son was never a hindrance in his mission. Mary brought forth Jesus by the power of the Spirit. So too, a faithful community brings forth Jesus in and through the Spirit which they have received in the sacraments.

The Pentecost event shows that God desires that the Church, as a faithful community, reproduce itself by reproducing its constitutive acts of Christian meaning and value. The common meaning of Christ event constitutes the Church but her self-realizing herself in the history is the result of dialectic interaction between God's communication and human response.

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